

Infrared and Proton Magnetic Resonance Spectral Studies on Tetradentate N,N' -ethylenebis(aceto-acetanilideimines)[†]

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β -Ketoamines, namely, N,N' -ethylenebis(acetoacetanilideimine), N,N' -ethylenebis(2-chloroacetoacetanilideimine), N,N' -ethylenebis(3-chloroacetoacetanilideimine), N,N' -ethylenebis(2,4-dichloroacetoacetanilideimine), N,N' -ethylenebis(2,5-dichloroacetoacetanilideimine), N,N' -ethylenebis(2-methoxyacetoacetanilideimine), N,N' -ethylenebis(4-methoxyacetoacetanilideimine) and N,N' -ethylenebis(2,5-dimethoxyacetoacetanilideimine) have been synthesized for the first time and characterized by elemental analyses, ir and pmr spectral studies. These studies revealed that these compounds exist as ketoamines with the two amino NH groups forming intramolecular hydrogen bonds of unequal strength with the carbonyl groups. The non-planar six membered rings thus formed lie at an angle to one another with respect to the bridging ethylenic C-C bond. An explanation for the unusual 'triplet' observed in the pmr spectra of N,N' -ethylenebis(acetylacetoneimine) and the above compounds has been offered.

THE ir spectra of N,N' -ethylenebis(acetylacetoneimine), related ligands and their transition metal chelates have been extensively studied in solid state¹⁻⁴. These ligands are Capable of existing in three tautomeric forms. (Fig. 1/A to C).

Fig. 1

Ueno and Martell¹ studied the ir spectra of N,N' -ethylenebis(acetylacetoneimine) and similar ligands and came to the conclusion that these compounds exist predominantly as the ketoamine form A and enolimine form B (Fig. 1). Dudek and Holm⁵ studied the pmr spectra of N,N' -ethylenebis(acetylacetoneimine) and N,N' -ethylenebis(benzoylacetoneimine) and concluded that they exist mostly (>95%) in ketoamine form (Fig. 1-A). The ketoimine structure (Fig. 1-C) was ruled out on the basis of the relatively low value of C=O stretching frequency in the ir spectra and the absence of a signal for the α -methylene protons in the pmr spectra. The conclusion on the ketoamine was largely based on the appearance of an

unusual 'triplet' (found in those β -ketoamines formed by the condensation of diamines and β -diketones) arising from the coupling of methylene protons with the proton on nitrogen as established by deuteration. However, no adequate explanation was offered on the origin of 'triplet', particularly its unusual structure.

With a view to establish the influence of the anilide moiety on the above tautomerization, the ir and pmr spectra of the eight new β -ketoamines along with N,N' -ethylenebis(acetylacetoneimine) were studied. Furthermore, it was also intended to study the possible intramolecular hydrogen bonding as well as conformations due to rotation around the bridging C-C bond. The NH/OH stretching frequencies in solution have been analyzed in detail to understand the nature of the 'triplet' found by Dudek and Holm⁵ and also observed in the pmr spectra of the compounds presented here.

Experimental

Acetoacetanilide (Sisco-Chem, Bombay) was purified by recrystallization. Ethylenediamine (Riedel) was distilled and stored in air-tight bottles. Chloro- and methoxy-substituted acetoacetanilides, used in the synthesis of β -ketoamines, were prepared by reported method⁶.

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer Model 221 equipped with sodium chloride-grating optics. The solution spectra in CCl_4 were recorded using 1 cm path length quartz cell. The pmr spectra were recorded on Varian A-60 and T-60 spectrometers operating at 60 MHz with TMS as internal standard.

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TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF β -KETOAMINES

Compound		M.P. °C	C	H	N%
N,N'-ethylenebis-(acetylacetonsimine)	$C_{18}H_{20}N_2O_2$	110.112	65.31 (64.30)	9.02 (8.99)	12.29 (12.49)
	I	209-10	70.46 (71.42)	7.08 (6.92)	13.14 (14.80)
II	$C_{22}H_{24}N_4O_2Cl_2$	148-150	59.46 (59.05)	6.02 (5.41)	12.39 (12.52)
III	$C_{22}H_{24}N_4O_2Cl_2$	190	58.78 (59.05)	5.41 (5.41)	12.25 (12.52)
IV	$C_{22}H_{24}N_4O_2Cl_4$	163-4	51.31 (51.17)	4.10 (4.30)	10.91 (10.85)
V	$C_{22}H_{24}N_4O_2Cl_4$	163	51.30 (51.17)	4.36 (4.30)	10.96 (10.85)
VI	$C_{18}H_{20}N_4O_2$	176-8°	65.49 (65.75)	6.49 (6.91)	12.45 (12.77)
VII	$C_{22}H_{20}N_4O_2$	195	64.85 (65.75)	6.49 (6.91)	12.40 (12.77)
VIII	$C_{22}H_{14}N_4O_2$	180	62.43 (62.66)	7.29 (8.82)	10.84 (11.25)

Roman letters represents the compounds presented in Fig. 2. Calculated values are given in the parenthesis.

TABLE 2—INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (cm^{-1}) OF THE β -KETOAMINES IN NUJOL MULL

EBAI	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	Possible assignment
	3295s	3395m	3290s	3422m	3410m 3402m	3415m 3320m	3375s 3355vs	3415w 3370m 3345s	} NH amide
3230m 3170m	3220m 3122m	3235w 3125w	3220m 3150w	3245w 3155vw	3230w 3155w	3230w 3140vw	3255m 3150w	3235w 3125w	
1610s 1580s	1645m 1600s	1610s 1590s	1600s 1590s	1650m 1600sh 1580m 1590s	1650m 1600s 1590s	1640s 1600s	1640m 1600s	1640sh 1600s	} C=O (Amide I) C=C C=C (Aromatic)
1540m	1550s 1510s	1520s 1510s	1525s	1510sh 1505sh	1510s	1530sh 1520s	1550sh 1520s	1545s 1520sh 1480s	
1480s	1480m 1445s	1490m 1440s	1480m 1440sh 1420s 1400sh	1485s 1480s	1480s	1480s	1500sh 1475s 1425s 1405m	1480s 1435sh 1420s	
1365m	1330s	1310s	1340sh 1320s	1320m	1340sh	1340s	1340sh	1330m	} CH ₃ wagging
1300s	1275w	1280s	1300s 1270s	1300m	1310s	1300s	1310s	1285s 1270s	
1260m	1250m	1245m	1260m	1270sh	1240m	1255m 1230m	1250m 1235m	1250sh 1230s,b	
1230m 1210m 1180m	1205s 1190w 1170w 1145m	1220m 1190s 1150w 1125s	1200s 1180m 1150s	1220w 1190s 1160m	1190m 1150s 1130m	1190sh 1180s 1150s 1135m	1183s 1198m	1180s 1170sh 1140s 1095w	} C=C + C-CH ₃ OH in plane bend (Arom.) O-CH ₃ (methoxy)
1100m	1130sh 1100w	1075m	1100w 1090w	1100m 1070m	1100m 1070m	1125sh			
1030m	1040m 1010w	1045m	1060m 1045sh	1050w	1050m	1060s 1040s	1030m	1055s 1030m	} CH ₃ rocking ring breathing OH in plane bend (Arom)
990m	983w 975w	1005m	1010m 990sh 970m	980w	1010w 980w 970w	1005m 970m	1005m 970w	1005m 985m	
955m 940m	910w	950m	920m		900m	925w 942w	970w	965m 905w	} C-OH ₂

Table 2—Contd.

EBAI	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	Possible assignment
865s		890m	895w	880m	890m	885w	875w	875m	} CH ₂ rocking OH out of plane def. (Aromatic)
848s	870w	870w	885w	860w	850w	855w	850m	890m	
805w		810w	800s	815w	800m	768s	845m		
	765m	760s				755s	885m		
							820w		} CH out of plane deformation
770s	785m	780s	790s	775m	785m	795w	780m	795m	
752s			780s		775m	788s	774w	785m	} CH out of plane def. vib. (Arom.)
	705w	725w	710m	745m	795m		755w	788m	
		705m	685w	780ah	725m	705m	735w	715m	
				705w					} C—Cl

Preparation of β -ketoamines

Acetoacetanilide (0.2 mole) in 250 ml absolute alcohol was heated to boiling on a water-bath under reflux and reacted with an alcoholic solution of ethylenediamine (0.1 mole). A white compound appeared within 5 minutes but the mixture was refluxed for 30 minutes, cooled, filtered, washed several times with 10-15 ml portions of cold alcohol and air dried.

All the substituted β -ketoamines were similarly prepared from substituted acetoacetanilides and ethylenediamine in 2:1 molar ratio. The yield ranged from 80-90%. The elemental analyses and melting points are given in Table 1. The following β -ketoamines were prepared (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2.

- I R=R'=H
- II R=R'=2-chloro-
- III R=R'=3-chloro-
- IV R=R'=2,4-dichloro-
- V R=R'=2,5-dichloro-
- VI R=R'=2-methoxy-
- VII R=R'=4-methoxy-
- VIII R=R'=2,5-dimethoxy-

Results and Discussion

The ir spectral data for the new β -ketoamines, recorded in Nujol mull, are presented in Table 2, with their assignments.

The ir spectra of compounds II, IV, V, VI, VIII (Fig. 2) and N, N'-ethylenebis(acetylacetoneimine) (EBAI) were recorded in the region 3700-2350 cm^{-1} in dilute carbon tetrachloride solution ($\sim 10^{-4}M$) using 1 cm path length quartz cells (Figs. 3, 4). The spectra of the first five compounds are similar to one another and have a sharp strong band at $\sim 3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and two medium bands in the 3250-3150 cm^{-1} region. Since the known compound, EBAI showed only two bands at 3220 and 3170 cm^{-1} , the band at $\sim 3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is ascribable to amide NH group. In order to characterize

the bands in the region 3250-3150 cm^{-1} N, N'-ethylenebis(2, 5-dichloroacetoacetanilideimine) and EBAI (Fig. 3) were deuterated *in situ* in carbon tetrachloride solution when new bands appeared at 2530, 2440 and 2375 cm^{-1} and 2440 and 2385 cm^{-1} respectively. Thus the bands at ~ 3400 , 3240 and 3150 cm^{-1} have their origin in either NH/OH stretching modes.

In order to establish which of the three tautomers gave rise to these bands, the pmr spectra of N, N'-ethylenebis(2, 5-dichloroacetoacetanilideimine) (Fig. 5) and EBAI were recorded in CCl_4 . Dudek and Holm⁵ had studied EBAI and shown that the $-\text{CH}_2-$ protons of the ethylene bridge were split into an unusual 'triplet' at 3.43 δ (the end signals were stronger than the middle one) which simplified into a singlet on N-deuteration. These authors concluded that EBAI exists as ketoamine tautomer to an extent of $>80\%$ in view of the absence of any signal due to ketoimine tautomer, particularly $-\text{CH}_2-$ of $-\text{COCH}_2\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$. Our studies on the pmr spectra of compounds II, IV, V, VI and VIII (Table 3) showed similar $-\text{CH}_2-$ triplets at 3.27-3.58 δ ($J=5-7 \text{ Hz}$). Furthermore, in compounds V and EBAI it was found that the $-\text{CH}_2-$ signal collapsed into a singlet on N-deuteration. There were no signals ascribable to the α -methylene protons of ketoimine structure in these spectra. In the enolimine tautomer (Fig. 1-B) the band due to intramolecularly hydrogen bonded hydroxyl should appear below 3000 cm^{-1} and usually^{7, 8} near 2700-2600 cm^{-1} . We have obtained¹⁰ the bonded hydroxyl band in N, N'-ethylenebis(salicylaldehydeimine) at 2750 cm^{-1} which is in agreement with the observation of Ueno and Martell⁹. The absence of such a band in the ir spectra of the present compounds shows the absence of enolimine species. These results thus establish that the present compounds exist almost exclusively in the ketoamine form and the tautomerization is little affected by anilide substitutions.

Under the circumstances, the two medium strong bands at 3250-3150 cm^{-1} would have their origin in the NH stretching modes of ethylenediamine moiety. From the average shift of about 250 cm^{-1} from the free NH band, it is evident that the two

Fig. 3. Infrared Spectra of

- (I) —N,N'-Ethylenedis (Acetylacetonimine)
...N,N'-Ethylenedis (Acetylacetonimine) after Deuteration
- (II) —N,N'-Ethylenedis (2,5-dichloroacetoacetanilideimine)
...N,N'-Ethylenedis (2,5-dichloroacetoacetanilideimine) After Deuteration in CCl₄ solution

Fig. 4. Infrared Spectra of

- (I) N,N'-Ethylenedis (2-chloroacetoacetanilideimine)
- (II) N,N'-Ethylenedis (2,4-dichloroacetoacetanilideimine)
- (III) N,N'-Ethylenedis (2-methoxyacetoacetanilideimine)
- (IV) N,N'-Ethylenedis (2,5-dimethoxyacetoacetanilideimine) in CCl₄ solution (1 cm quartz cell)

TABLE 3—CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF β-KETOAMINES

Compounds	Solvent	Chemical shifts, ppm(δ) and coupling constants, j, (Hz)										
		-CH ₃	-CH ₂	-OH	-OCH ₃	Aromatic protons					Ar-NH-	-NH bonded
						2-H	3-H	4-H	5-H	6-H		
N,N'-ethylenedis-(acetylacetonimine)	CCl ₄	1.90	3.43	4.85								10.97
I	DMSO	1.98				7.56	7.2	6.86	7.2	7.56	9.03	9.16
		1.96(s)	8.27	4.61(s)								(t,j=6.0)
II	ODCl ₃	2.0(s)	3.37	4.47(s)			7.97	6.83	7.00	8.33	7.00	9.33
			(t,j=5.0)									
	DMSO			4.76(s)			7.90	6.90	7.06	8.00	8.13	9.16
III	DMSO	1.93(s)	3.51	4.55(s)		7.88		6.85	7.16	7.33	9.15	9.15
			(t,j=6.0)									(t,j=6.0)
IV	ODCl ₃	1.97(s)	3.43	4.50(s)			7.33		7.16	8.33	7.03	9.40
			(t,j=7.0)									
V	DMSO			4.76			7.43		7.23	8.06	8.90	9.16
				4.50			7.20	6.87		8.50	7.05	9.40
	ODCl ₃	2.00	3.40									
			(t,j=7.0)									
VI	CCl ₄	1.93	3.43	4.45			7.30	6.83		8.50	7.00	9.45
	DMSO			4.81			7.35	6.96		8.14	8.33	9.14
	ODCl ₃	1.97	3.40	4.47	3.97		6.53	6.95	6.53	8.31	7.13	9.36
			(t,j=6.0)									
VII	DMSO	1.90		4.72	3.83		6.91	6.91	6.91	8.13	7.96	9.00
	DMSO	1.92		4.56	3.70	7.51	6.80		6.80	7.51	8.95	9.21
VIII	ODCl ₃	1.97	3.43	4.50	3.80		6.70	6.40		8.03	7.21	9.37
			(t,j=6.0)		3.83							
	DMSO			4.70			6.78	6.36		7.85	7.85	9.16

s=singlet, t=triplet

Fig. 5. PMR Spectrum of *N,N'*-Ethylenebis(2,5-dichloroacetanilideimine) in CCl_4 .

NH groups of the ketoamine structure are hydrogen bonded. The intramolecular nature of the hydrogen bonding was confirmed by a dilution study which showed no change in the position of these two bands. The pmr signals for the NH at $\sim 9.4 \delta$ in these compounds (Table 3) also indicate that they are hydrogen bonded. The difference in the positions of the two bands of 50 cm^{-1} in case of EBAI and $80\text{--}90 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the compounds II, IV, V, VI and VIII suggest that the two amino groups are intramolecularly hydrogen bonded to the carbonyl groups with different strengths forming six membered rings. However, the average NH shift of 250 cm^{-1} indicates that the intramolecular hydrogen bonds are not particularly strong (cf. $\Delta \nu$ of $\sim 850 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ketoenol tautomers of acetylacetone⁷) and may not result in conjugate chelation leading to the planarity of the rings. This could lead to the rotation of the NH group around the C—N bond as suggested earlier⁶. When such non-equivalent amino NH protons couple with $-\text{CH}_2-$ protons, doublets of unequal intensity result and their superpositions could lead to the unusual 'triplet' observed in EBAI and in the present compounds.

The absorptions in the double bond region, though complex due to the presence of aromatic moiety, suggest that the C=O group is involved in intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The highest frequency band ascribable to the carbonyl group

is found at $\sim 1640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the β -ketoamines, except in 2-chloro and 3-chloro derivatives in which it occurs at 1610 and 1620 cm^{-1} and in EBAI at $\sim 1610 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The shift of only $\sim 20\text{--}40 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ from the amide C=O of 1660 cm^{-1} is also in agreement with the moderate intramolecular hydrogen bonding present in these compounds, though considerable mixing among the C=O and C=C modes would obviate the true shift.

The pmr spectral studies of these ligands in three solvents are presented in Table 3. The unusual 'triplet' due to ethylenediamine moiety was found unchanged in DMSO both in its pattern and position. The chemical shift of the amide NH proton which appeared as a sharp singlet, however, showed considerable shift in position ($7.21\text{--}9.03 \delta$). The chemical shift of amide NH would depend on hydrogen bonding which differs from solvent to solvent. Thus, it may tend to associate in solvents like CCl_4 or CHCl_3 , or be hydrogen bonded to the S=O of the DMSO bringing about considerable change in chemical shift. The chemical shift of the intramolecularly bonded NH group appeared in the low field region at 9.1 to 9.5δ as a broad signal in the three solvents. Both the amide NH and amino NH groups exchanged with D_2O , but as expected the intramolecularly bonded amino NH exchange was slow and went to completion in ~ 24 hrs. The nearly identical spectra of these compounds in the

9.1 to 9.5 δ region suggest that the tautomerisation is unaffected by DMSO.

The =CH- proton was found at $\sim 4.45 \delta$ in CDCl_3 and at 4.7δ in DMSO in most of the compounds. This proton was easily exchanged on D_2O addition in compound V while in acetylacetone, acetoacetanilide and EBAI there was hardly any exchange seen even after keeping for 36 hrs. The exchange studies, however, could not be extended to other compounds of the present series due to precipitation on addition of D_2O to their CCl_4 solution. The easy exchange of =CH- proton in the present compounds suggests that anilide substitution facilitate protonation-deprotonation exchange phenomenon.

Their spectra of compounds I, III and VII which were insoluble in CCl_4 were recorded in Nujol mull (Table 2). The spectra of I and III showed a broad band at $\sim 3290 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which was probably ascribable to the amide NH. The broad bands in the region $3220\text{-}3100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are ascribable to the hydrogen bonded amino NH groups. The spectrum of VII showed unusually well resolved bands at 3378, 3333 and 3255 cm^{-1} .

The ir and pmr spectral studies reported in this paper thus show that the unusual 'triplet' is due to the coupling of the unequally hydrogen bonded

amino NH protons with the protons of $-\text{CH}_2-$ groups and the six membered rings formed by the intramolecular hydrogen bonding between the NH and carbonyl groups are non-planar and non-equivalent.

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